

CLASSIFICATION OF SOME DIDACTIC GAMES USED IN PRIMARY CLASS MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract. *In the content of this article, some didactic games and their classification used in the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy of the primary grade are discussed based on the information collected as a result of research and literature.*

Keywords: *didactic game, primary school students, student personality formation, educational process, effective method.*

Games are the main activity of students, especially elementary school students. Games are an important tool in forming the personality of students. In it, the student is formed in every way. It has a positive effect on the results of the educational process. Games have educational aspects, such as concentration of attention, strengthening of memory, complete thinking, being kind to each other, valuing the team, loyalty, aspiration, evaluating each other's opinion. In addition, during the game, it creates an environment for students to form a team, establish cooperation and friendship, communicate, and agree. This will make the students more united.

It is known that among the various games used in working with students at school, there are: role-playing (plot role-playing) and didactic games. It should also be noted that these games have different effects on each student. In particular, role-playing games are characterized by the fact that students together with the teacher become performers of certain roles. Role-playing games develop fantasy, imagination and speech, and are of great importance in moral education.

If we talk about didactic games, didactic games are specially created by teachers for educational purposes, they are cognitive and developmental. Word games, travel lessons, KVN, quiz lessons, etc. are widely used in school practice.

There are other classifications of games. Determining the character of the game in the primary grade mother tongue and reading literacy classes is necessary to set a didactic goal for the students, as well as to analyze whether this goal has been achieved as a result of the game.

In the book "Games in the Russian language class" written by the famous Russian scientist L.V.Petranovskaya, one can witness that the author distinguishes educational, combinatory, analytical, associative, contextual, linguistic and creative games. At this point, it is necessary to give a more precise description of the games that have the characteristics of this list.

Educational, that is, educational games are the simplest and most traditional games that help to consolidate the learned material and acquire stable skills in applying knowledge. For example, games containing a task such as "Find as many test words as possible for a given word in a certain time!" are among educational games.

Combinatorial games are very popular games in which the player works with the material side of a linguistic symbol, usually a word. These games require the ability to quickly and efficiently calculate options and choose combinations.

Analytical games are learning that develops analytical thinking, free, uninhibited, but at the same time helps to acquire the skills of correct logical analysis, learn to see patterns, commonalities and differences, cause and effect. are games.

Associative games - they encourage the student to engage in associative thinking, look for comparisons, guess clues.

Contextual games are games that focus students on the complex semantic relationships in the text, interpret, understand what is not directly expressed, and vice versa, use information in different ways. develops the ability to deliver.

Linguistic games are games in which players, or rather, student-players, experiment with language units and patterns. Although they are the most important to achieve the structure of the language, these games are developed to a lesser extent.

Creative tasks, that is, creative games, are various writing tasks, usually depending on more or less difficult conditions, which, on the one hand, contribute to the development of imagination and ingenuity in the use of language tools. On the other hand, he comments and critically evaluates the students' creative works.

From the point of view of the nature of the pedagogical process, educational, controlling and summarizing games are distinguished in educational processes. That is, it is cognitive, educational, developmental; reproductive, productive, creative; communicative, diagnostic, career guidance, psychotechnical games are provided.

According to the game environment, the teacher should not forget that there are games played with objects and without objects, desktop, indoor and outdoor, computer and television, and finally, technical, vehicles. Keeping this in mind is of great importance in predicting the effectiveness of using the game type and tool in which part of the learning process. Among the games that involve playing with objects in elementary mother tongue and reading literacy classes, the use of ball games and similar tools is the most effective. But keep in mind that a ball game requires more open space than a classroom with three rows of tables.

All the games that can be used in the elementary mother tongue and reading literacy classes can be organized in two ways:

Method 1. Conduct board games, indoor games with handouts for each table or each student at the table without changing the arrangement of the furniture and the position of the students. These include lotto, crosswords (as well as scanwords and chainwords), riddles, metagrams, anagrams, etc.

Method 2. Furniture in the classroom is changed according to the number of teams (chairs are placed around changed tables) or according to the principle of "playing field" - "judges" - «spectators».

We know that didactic games can be played at different stages of the lesson. At the beginning of the lesson, the purpose of the game is to organize and interest children, to stimulate their activity, and in the middle of the lesson, the didactic game should solve the problem of mastering the subject. At the end of the lesson, the game can have a discovery character. These goals should always be kept in mind, because this will help in the effective service of each didactic game used in the course of the lesson.

Based on the above-mentioned points and information, it can be concluded that being aware of the classification of didactic games used in the processes of each organized lesson helps the teacher organizing the lesson in organizing the lesson at a high level and, most importantly, at the

intended high level. helps to achieve results. And this does not only serve the interests of the teacher. It also serves to increase students' interest in lessons. In particular, it is the basis for the high level of students' enthusiasm in the future lesson processes and the intensity of their participation processes. It can be added that the use of didactic games in the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy in primary education helps to eliminate a number of difficulties associated with memorizing the material to one degree or another, to develop the material at the level of emotional awareness. This undoubtedly contributes to the development of cognitive interest in the subject of mother tongue and reading literacy in the student.

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